

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS^a

Compd. no.	X	Y	Z	M.p. ^a °C	Yield (%)	Mol. formula
2a	2-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	6-H	231 ^a	83	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S
2b	2-NO ₂	4-Br	6-H	192 ^b	91	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ SBr
2c	2-NO ₂	4-Cl	6-H	177 ^b	95	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ SOCl
2d	2-NO ₂	4-CF ₃	6-NO ₂	194 ^b	93	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄ SF ₃
2e	2-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	5-F	106 ^b	95	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄ SF
3a	2-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	6-H	186 ^c	99	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₄ S
3b	2-NO ₂	4-Br	6-H	189 ^c	88	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ SBr
3c	2-NO ₂	4-Cl	6-H	111 ^a	86	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ SOCl
3d	2-NO ₂	4-CF ₃	6-NO ₂	181 ^b	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₄ SF ₃
3e	2-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	5-F	151 ^c	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₄ SF
4a	2-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	6-H	144 ^a	70	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂
4b	2-NO ₂	4-Br	6-H	101 ^a	67	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Br
4c	2-NO ₂	4-Cl	6-H	120 ^c	71	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Cl
4d	2-NO ₂	4-CF ₃	6-NO ₂	159 ^d	45	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ F ₃
4e	2-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	5-F	200 ^a	40	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ F
5a	2-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	6-H	156 ^c	45	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂
5b	2-NO ₂	4-Br	6-H	149 ^d	30 ^c	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Br
5c	2-NO ₂	4-Cl	6-H	149 ^a	30	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Cl
5d	2-NO ₂	4-CF ₃	6-NO ₂	133 ^c	35	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ F ₃
5e	2-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	5-F	162 ^c	39	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ F
6a	2-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	6-H	116 ^a	53	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₄ SOCl
6b	2-NO ₂	4-Br	6-H	110 ^d	40	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ SBrCl
6c	2-NO ₂	4-Cl	6-H	135 ^a	46	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ SOCl
6d	2-NO ₂	4-CF ₃	6-NO ₂	156 ^f	65	C ₂₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ SOClF ₃

^aCompounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

^bSolvent of crystallisation : ^aethanol, ^bethanol/H₂O, ^cacetone, ^dchloroform/petroleum ether, ^ebenzene, ^fmethanol.

The structures of **6** were established on the basis of their elemental analysis (Table 1) and ir spectra which showed a band at $\sim 1730\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=O, β -lactam) besides the other characteristic bands.

Biological screening: The compounds were tested *in vitro* for their growth inhibitory activity against a variety of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, namely, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas fluorescence*, *Escherichia coli* and *Serratia marcescens*. The antibacterial activity of the tested compounds was performed using the disc-diffusion technique⁹ at concentration of 0.1 mg ml⁻¹. The results showed that compounds **4a–e** exhibited fair activity whereas compound **5d** had potent activity against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*. Compounds **6a, b** showed medium activity against *B. cereus* and low activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. fluorescence*.

Experimental

Melting points were uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137B spectrophotometer. Completion of the reaction and purity of the compounds were checked by tlc.

4-Aminodiaryl sulphides (1): These were prepared according to the reported method¹.

4-[N-[p-(Diarylthio)]formimidoyl]quinoline (2): Condensation of 4-aminodiaryl sulphide (0.01 mol) with quinoline-4-carboxaldehyde in the presence of dimethyl sulphoxide (2–3 ml) was conducted by heating for 1.5–2 h. The reaction mixture was

left overnight and then triturated with ethanol and purified by crystallisation from the proper solvent.

4-[N-[p-(Diarylthio)]formimidoyl]pyrrole (3): 4-Aminodiphenyl sulphide (0.01 mol) was heated gently with pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde (0.01 mol) for 3 h. The target products were separated and purified as before.

Substituted-thiazolidinones (4 and 5): A mixture of **2** and/or **3** (0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (30 ml) was refluxed for 5–20 h with the removal of water via Dean-Stark trap. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was purified by crystallisation from the proper solvent; in some cases the thiazolidinones separated directly from the solvent.

1-[p-(Diarylthio)]-3-chloro-4-(4-quinolyl)-2-azetidione (6): Monochloroacetyl chloride (0.02 mol) was added dropwise at room temperature to a well-stirred solution of the sulphidoanil (**3**; 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) in dry dioxan (30 ml). The mixture was stirred for 6 h, left at room temperature for 5 days, and the resulting precipitate (triethylammonium chloride) was filtered and washed thoroughly with dioxan. The washing was combined with the filtrate, concentrated under reduced pressure to minimum volume and poured into cold water (30 ml). The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from the proper solvent.

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